

Synthesis and Reactions of Pyridinium Iodides of Substituted Acetophenones

D. R. Gupta and A. C. Ojha

The present communication concerns with the synthesis of pyridinium iodides of 2 : 4 dihydroxy-, 2 : 5 dihydroxy-, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-, 2 hydroxy-5-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-5-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl 5-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo, 2-bromo-4-nitro-, *p* nitro acetophenones and naphthyl methylketone.

Krohnke and Krohnke¹ reported the synthesis of anils through the reaction of sodium cyanide with nitrones which were obtained on condensing pyridinium iodides of acetophenones with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline². Practically no work seems to have been done on pyridinium iodides of substituted acetophenones. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesise pyridinium iodides (II) from substituted acetophenones (I) by reacting acetophenones with iodine and pyridine. The probable reaction for the formation of pyridinium iodides may be suggested as follows :—

whence

These pyridinium iodides have been characterised by the formation of derivatives such as oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones. The effect of different substituents present in the benzene nucleus of the acetophenones has also been investigated.

Synthesis of Pyridinium Iodides of Substituted Acetophenones : Substituted acetophenones (0.08 mol), iodine (0.07 mol) and pyridine (0.08 mol) were mixed together and were refluxed on water bath for about 2 hrs. and the reaction mixture was allowed to cool. A solid mass was thus obtained and to it acetone (0.1 mol) was then added. On cooling at 0°, the crystals of pyridinium iodides of substituted acetophenones were obtained. The products thus obtained were crystallised from ethanol. The characteristics of pyridinium iodides are described in table 1.

1. F. Krohnke and G. Krohnke, *Chem. Ber.*, 1958, **91**, 1474.
2. D. R. Gupta, Y. Singh and H. D. Tayal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **2**, 164.

TABLE I

Synthesis of Pyridinium Iodides of Substituted Acetophenones

Pyridinium Iodides of-	Colour	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen		% Halogen	
					Required	Found	Required	Found
1. 2 : 4-dihydroxy aceto-phenone	Brown	168	72	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ NO ₃ I	—	—	35.57	35.18
2. 2 : 5-dihydroxy aceto-phenone	Brown	135	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ NO ₃ I	—	—	35.57	35.20
3. 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone	Brown	162	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ NO ₂ I	—	—	36.05	35.80
4. 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone	Light Brown	142	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂ ClI	—	—	41.38	41.05
5. 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone	Camel	157	40	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂ BrI	—	—	49.48	49.23
6. 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone	Yellow	182	45	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂ ClI	—	—	41.72	41.56
7. 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro acetophenone	Pink	176	40	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂ ClBrI	—	—	53.35	53.01
8. 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-bromo acetophenone	Reddish	160	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂ BrI	—	—	55.83	55.20
9. 2-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo acetophenone	Buff	158	42	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂ Br ₂ I	—	—	57.55	57.13
10. 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo acetophenone	Camel	172	40	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂ ClBrI	—	—	53.35	53.06
11. 2-bromo-4-nitro acetophenone	Buff	161	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ BrI	—	—	46.10	45.90
12. <i>p</i> -nitro acetophenone	Yellow	158	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ I	—	—	41.12	40.02
13. Naphthyl methyl ketone	Camel	149	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NOI	—	—	38.86	33.66

Melting point uncorrected.

Formation of Derivatives : Phenylhydrazones, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, oximes and semicarbazones of the pyridinium iodides were prepared by the usual methods and were obtained almost in theoretical yield. Oximes and semicarbazones were crystallized from alcohol while hydrazones were crystallized from chloroform and toluene. The characteristics of oximes, hydrazones and semicarbazones are given in table II and III.

These pyridinium iodides are soluble in acetone, chloroform, acetonitrile and 50% ethanol, but practically insoluble in water.

It is quite interesting to note that the presence of various substituents in the benzene ring of the acetophenones exerts much influence on the yield. When the nitro groups are present at para positions, the yield is approximately 80%. The yield varies from 70 to 75% when two hydroxyl groups are attached to 2 : 4 or 2 : 5 positions. When two halogen atoms are present along with one hydroxyl group, the yield varies approximately from 40 to 60%.

TABLE II

Derivatives of Pyridinium Iodides of Substituted Acetophenones.

Pyridinium Iodides of-	Colour	OXIMES			SEMI-CARBAZONES			
		M.P. °C	% Halogen Required Found		Colour	M.P. °C	% Halogen Required Found	
1. 2 : 4-Hydroxy acetophenone	Brown	188	34.14	33.72	Grey	178	30.67	30.12
2. 2 : 5-Dihydroxy acetophenone	Red	168	34.14	33.68	Brown	169	30.67	30.06
3. 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone	Yellow	172	34.32	34.02	Brown	174	30.82	30.61
4. 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone	Brown	180	41.61	40.04	Brown	168	37.57	37.02
5. 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone	Orange	186	47.58	47.36	Red	180	43.39	43.01
6. 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone	Orange	176	40.17	39.74	Brown	175	36.40	36.02
7. 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro acetophenone	Red	190	52.08	51.16	Red	172	47.40	47.08
8. 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-bromo acetophenone	Red	174	54.25	54.01	Brown	178	50.26	50.01
9. 2-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo acetophenone	Orange	183	55.83	55.42	Brown	168	51.61	51.42
10. 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo acetophenone	Orange	179	52.08	51.19	Red	166	47.40	47.15
11. 2-bromo-4-nitro acetophenone	Red	168	44.61	44.04	Red	174	40.90	40.16
12. <i>p</i> -nitro acetophenone	Red	169	33.00	32.54	Red	160	29.74	29.22
13. Naphthyl methyl ketone	Grey	182	32.60	32.02	Brown	158	28.60	27.48

Melting point uncorrected.

TABLE III

Derivatives of Pyridinium Iodides of Substituted Acetophenones.

Pyridinium Iodides of-	Colour	PHENYL HYDRAZONES			2 : 4-DINITRO PHENYL HYDRAZONES			
		M.P. °C	% Halogen Required Found		Colour	M.P. °C	% Halogen Required Found	
1. 2 : 4-dihydroxy acetophenone	Red	169	28.41	28.14	Red	198	23.65	22.86
2. 2 : 5-dihydroxy acetophenone	Brown	180	28.41	28.08	Red	186	23.65	23.03
3. 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone	Red	185	28.54	28.28	Red	194	23.70	23.18
4. 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone	Yellow	182	35.68	33.16	Brown	188	29.25	28.88
5. 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone	Red	178	39.28	38.28	Brown	193	34.50	34.00
6. 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone	Brown	188	32.92	32.28	Red	196	28.53	28.08
7. 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro acetophenone	Red	192	44.71	44.58	Red	202	38.21	37.54
8. 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-bromo acetophenone	Red	182	47.51	47.02	Red	195	41.35	41.02
9. 2-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo acetophenone	Red	176	48.72	48.46	Brown	188	42.26	41.86
10. 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo acetophenone	Brown	184	44.71	44.56	Red	190	38.21	37.82
11. 2-bromo-4-nitro acetophenone	Red	192	37.28	36.76	Brown	200	32.90	32.15
12. <i>p</i> -nitro acetophenone	Yellow	178	26.65	26.22	Red	184	23.09	22.28
13. Naphthyl methyl ketone	Yellow	162	26.51	26.05	Red	172	22.84	22.22

Melting point uncorrected.

The pyridinium iodides on condensation with *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline and subsequent treatment with a 10% sodium cyanide solution produced α -cyano aroyl anils.

Further work is in progress on the synthesis of different α -cyano aroyl anils from the pyridinium iodides.

The authors are thankful to Shri R. N. Gupta, Principal, Hindu College, Moradabad and Prof. M. K. Jain, Principal, Sahu Jain College, Najibabad for encouragement.

Department of Chemistry,
U.P. Agricultural University,
Pantnagar. (Nainital)

and

Department of Chemistry,
Sahu Jain College,
Najibabad. (U.P.)

Received April 17. 1971